

Metal-based ionic liquids : Their properties, applications and future prospects[†]

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Abstract : Metal-based ionic liquids (M-ILs) is new emerging class of ionic liquids. M-ILs comprises of various transition metals or lanthanides either in cations or anions. The involvement of such metals makes them a new type of ILs materials which have properties similar to conventional ILs such as low vapour pressure, high thermal stability, and high ionic conductivity with additional features such as magnetic responsiveness and luminescence activity. Due to such amazing properties, M-ILs have been gained considerable attention in scientific community for applied research. In this review, we have drafted a general introduction, idea about involved cations and metals, brief discussion on characterization of metal containing anions and have outlined the important scopes in catalysis, nanomaterial synthesis, colloidal formulation, biomass processing, micro-extraction process, magnetic separation of biomolecules, and other potential applications anticipated in future from M-ILs.

Keywords : Metal-based ionic liquids, paramagnetic ionic liquids, micro-emulsion, magnetic surfactants, magnetic susceptibility, PCR, micro-extraction.

1. Introduction

Currently, a major research drive is underway in industry and academia to substitute more environmentally friendly technologies for traditional ones in which damaging and volatile organic solvents are heavily used. The exponential growth of environmental issues year by year is a key point of research and discussion¹. The concept of Green Chemistry (also termed as a sustainable chemistry) now has been subjected to eliminate the toxic organic substance and promote the innovation of new zero waste technology for an industrial process². Thus, ILs (boon of green

chemistry) are considered as environmentally friendly efficient substitutes for such volatile toxic organic substance and solvents, not only because of their low vapour pressures but more importantly because of their ability to act as catalysts and good solvation nature. Apart from these the ILs hold several other attractive properties, including chemical and thermal stability, non-flammability, high ionic conductivity, and a wide electrochemical potential window.

ILs usually entail of inorganic anions and usually nitrogen-containing organic cations, and their chemical and physical properties can be finely tuned for a

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range of applications by varying the cations or anions. Varying the anion or cation their melting point, liquidus range and other property changes dramatically. For example if we replace Cl^- from Br^- to the $[\text{C}_4\text{mim}]^+$ cation then it will turn in to the liquid below room temperature or the hydrophilic nature with BF_4 can be a changed into hydrophobic nature via replacement with NTf_2 anion. This is how ILs with desired properties are accessible and have been explored in many applications.

The first generation of ILs was synthesized with chloroaluminate and another metal halide where 1,3-dialkyl imidazolium and N-alkyl pyridinium cations were at crowning³. The ILs of first-generation suffer several drawback including instability in water, not suitability for biotransformations, oxygen-sensitivity⁴ and hygroscopic nature⁵.

The shortcomings of first-generation ILs now have been overcome by the smart choice of cations, anions, or ligands. The use of transition and lanthanide metals in anionic part of ILs have come into picture due to versatile nature of these elements. It is well-known that transition and lanthanide metals are used for catalytic activity due to variable oxidation states. Inherent magnetic and optical properties are also a key factor for interest. Halometalate and coordination compounds of transition metals are also now have been used for task-specific ILs synthesis. Desired properties say magnetic, optical, luminescent, electrochemical and catalytic as an inherent in ILs anion of halometalate and organic ligand-metal complex have been used. These ILs, therefore, now has emerged as the new functional active class of ILs. Some reviews on magnetic, catalytic, pharmaceutical and energetic properties have been published⁶. Such anion or organic complex component ions allow the fine and dual tuning of liquid properties of the resulting ILs, by the chemical modification of both cation and anion.

In this review, we focus on various metal-based ionic liquids (M-ILs) which have been developed till now. The review comprises use of cations and anions containing metal to the synthesis of M-ILs, their characterization and their versatile applications.

2. Choice of cations and metals

Since there is numerous choice for cations and so many unique cations have been used to meet criteria of ILs for the desired applications. Four major classes of the cation are highlighted till date ammonium, imidazolium, pyridinium, sulfonium, and phosphonium.

Subsequently, more biodegradable ILs have been reported, including (cation as) amino acid-based chiral, cholinium cations, and dications. Moreover, ILs consisting of ammonium ions have also been reported, namely, Aliquat 336, long alkyl chain containing ammonium and imidazolium cations. Apart from these, other cations such as penthrolinium, guanidinium cation (Fig. 1) have also been reported.

The role of cations is very important if IL for a task specific application. For example, if the anionic part of IL is showing catalytic activity then the choice of cation should be in such a way that it dissolves all the reactants molecules. Combination of cation with any anions will be effective if they will show synergic effect, no adverse effect on activity of counter ion, able to reduce the melting point, able to reduce the negative effect of counter ion, low viscosity, inertness to moisture etc. A great choice of cation brings

Fig. 1. Various cations used to prepare metal-based ionic liquids.

the ability to solubilize a large array of diverse molecules along with the immiscibility both in water and nonpolar organic solvents which further adds to their usefulness in various streams of science.

Similarly, the choice of anions is also important if desired properties in the ILs are to be achieved. For anions, there is no tactic question for selection, based on property; metal can be chosen. Some transition metals like V, Mn, Cr, Co, Fe, Ni, and Zn are used in catalytic as well as magnetic applications. Some lanthanides including Eu, Yr, Tt are used as a luminescent reflector. Lanthanide Gd, Ho, and Dy are also used for magnetic properties.

In a class of halometalate, transition metal has been used as general formula $[MX_y]^{n-}$ where X is Cl, or Br. Whereas, in the class of organic metal complex, metal is chelated with appropriate ligand. Due to variable oxidation, transition and lanthanide metals can be used in cation or anion complex. Ferrocene-based ILs are example where Fe metal made cationic part of the IL. Apart from these, CN, NTf₂, and mixed halo based ILs are also reported. Anion, where mixed halides are used can be represented by formula $[MX_aY_b]^{n-}$ where X and Y are Cl or Br but $X \neq Y$.

3. Characterization

It is customary to elucidate the structure verification of ILs with various techniques. Mostly cationic part is organic hence it can be verified by NMR, IR and MS techniques. But where the anionic part which is mostly metal containing, ¹H NMR and MS techniques may not be suitable. UV-Visible and Raman spectroscopy has been used for complex elucidation.

Transition elements have transition electrons in their outer most shell which undergoes in transition when they absorb the UV/Visible light. For electronic transition in metals, Orgel and Tanabe-Sugano diagrams are useful. Orgel diagrams are used only for high spin complexes qualitatively whereas Tanabe-Sugano diagrams are useful both for high spin and low spin complexes. So electronic transition in the anionic metal complex can be explained via this diagram. In (Fig. 2) UV absorption spectra of 0.5 mM $[C_8mim]FeCl_4$ in acetonitrile is shown as representative for all

Fig. 2. UV absorption spectrum of $[C_8mim]FeCl_4$ (Synthesized and spectrum taken at CSIR-CSMCRI, Bhavnagar).

$[FeCl_4]^-$.

Fe^{III} , Mn^{II} have ad^5 system where five unpaired electrons collectively give equal contribution toward magnetic and spectral properties. Due to ⁶S, various spectral transitions are expected. Fig. 2 is showing three peaks for Fe^{III} when it was high spin tetrahedral structure. For the UV-Vis spectra of $[FeCl_4]^-$ anion, the characteristic band has appeared between 450 to 700 nm. At 529 nm peak appeared due to ${}^6A_1 \rightarrow {}^4T_2$, at 602 nm peak appeared due to ${}^6A_1 \rightarrow {}^4A_2$ and at 684 nm due to ${}^6A_1 \rightarrow {}^4T_2$. These are characteristic absorption bands for $[FeCl_4]^-$ anion. Regarding characterization by UV-Vis spectra of $[MnCl_4]^{2-}$, two sets of absorption bands were reported by Jared L. Anderson *et al.*⁷. The first group of absorption bands may be attributed to transitions to D-term states with strong ligand field splitting, whereas the second group of bands originates from small ligand-field-split G terms. In general, the bands of the G-terms appear with much lower intensities than those of the D-terms. These two bands appeared in the 335–500 nm region corresponding to the tetrahedral-coordinated $[MnCl_4]^{2-}$ anions⁸.

UV-Visible absorption spectroscopy is also used for metal halide like $[CuCl_4]^{2-}$, $[NiCl_4]^{2-}$, $[CoCl_4]^{2-}$. Here also two absorption bands have appeared one is related to the aromatic ring in UV region and another one due to electronic transitions. 432 nm for

$[\text{NiCl}_4]^{2-}$, 528 nm for $[\text{CuCl}_4]^{2-}$ and 682 nm for $[\text{CoCl}_4]^{2-}$ as reported by Seham A. Shaban *et al.*⁹.

Raman spectroscopy is an excellent tool to analyse the ionic species in their complex nature. Raman spectra can also sensitively reveal changes in molecular symmetry and are thus suited to the identification of species. Furthermore, the intensities of the Raman lines can be used to empirically relate the concentrations of species and one can calculate the solvation number of metal ions. The structural confirmation of complex anion such $[\text{FeCl}_4]^-$ anion can further done by Raman analysis as shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Raman scattering spectrum of FeCl_4 anion (Spectrum taken at CSIR-CSMCRI, Bhavnagar).

The characteristic band has appeared at 334 cm^{-1} which corresponds to the Fe-Cl vibration mode in $[\text{FeCl}_4]^-$. This value of 334 cm^{-1} belongs to the total symmetric vibration A_1 mode. In Fig. 3, except at 334 cm^{-1} absence of other peaks rules out the possibility of any dimerization originating from $[\text{FeCl}_4]^-$ anion. When a symmetric $[\text{FeCl}_4]^-$ anion is distorted and converted into asymmetric $[\text{FeCl}_3\text{Br}]^-$ anion by chemical means then other new Raman shift has been observed. The appearance of new bands at 224, 245, 273, 334, 349 due to Fe-Br bond and a shoulder at 400 (Fe-Cl) cm^{-1} is appeared¹⁰.

Raman spectra of the $[\text{MnCl}_4]^{2-}$ anion (Fig. 4) showed a characteristic absorption band at 251 cm^{-1} , which corresponds to symmetric vibrational stretch-

Fig. 4. Raman scattering spectrum of $[\text{MnCl}_4]^{2-}$ anion (Spectrum taken at CSIR-CSMCRI, Bhavnagar).

ing on bond (Mn-Cl)⁸. Similarly, other tetrahalide IL diethylammonium tetrachloroaurate $(\text{DEA})_2[\text{CuCl}_4]$ was studied by Christian Reber *et al.* They reported the A_1 symmetric stretching frequency and the T_2 frequency are 277 cm^{-1} and 188 cm^{-1} , respectively for bond (Cl-Cu) at room-temperature¹¹. Further, a zinc based anionic chloro complex was studied by Frank Endres *et al.* They observed the vibrational stretching frequency on Zn-Cl bond in $[\text{ZnCl}_4]^{2-}$ at $\sim 275\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The Raman vibration frequencies for $[\text{ZnCl}_3]^-$ can be found at ~ 285 and 348 cm^{-1} .

Seham A. Shaban *et al.* have been prepared various M-ILs and characterized by Raman spectroscopy⁹. The prepared $[\text{CoCl}_4]^{2-}$ has been distinguished by two broad absorption bands at 256.61 and 325.23 cm^{-1} assigned to the symmetric Co-Cl stretching vibration of $[\text{CoCl}_4]^{2-}$ anion¹². The Raman spectrum of $[\text{NiCl}_4]^{2-}$ exhibiting weak bands at 250 cm^{-1} is assigned to the symmetric Ni-Cl stretching vibration of $[\text{NiCl}_4]^{2-}$ anion (Fig. 5). Similar technique has been employed for other anion complex of metals to evaluate structure and bonding.

Although mass spectrometry has been commonly used as a technique for characterisation of ILs where positive and negative modes are used to characterize cation and anion of ILs, the anionic part of ILs being complex leads to erroneous conclusions, for example

Fig. 5. Raman scattering spectrum of $[\text{NiCl}_4]^{2-}$ anion (Spectrum taken at CSIR-CSMCRI, Bhavnagar).

about anionic speciation in chlorometallate ILs or any metal complex anion. Despite these drawbacks, some researchers have used this technique for characterization of metallohalide anion.

Fig. 6 shows the ESI-MS spectra of the synthesized metal-containing IL by Feng Yan *et al.* The intensive peaks corresponding to $[\text{CuCl}_2\text{Br}]^-$, $[\text{FeCl}_3\text{Br}]^-$, and $[\text{ZnCl}_2\text{Br}]^-$ can be observed at m/z 211, 239 and 212, respectively¹³. However presence of other peaks creates confusion to formation other complex.

4. Properties

The presence of transition metals as part of molecule have resulted in expected property of transition metals in ILs or have introduced the properties even with better performance. All the properties of transi-

tion metals including optical, spectral, magnetism, catalytic, electrochemical etc. have been introduced in ILs. Dependence on metal ion, property of IL can be tuned accordance to desired application. Like other ILs all M-ILs exhibit same properties including wide liquidus range, high thermal stability, non-flammability, less volatile, non-toxic nature, etc. Some M-ILs which are solid at room temperature also follows the criteria of ILs. But due to involvement of metals these show additional properties and some of them are briefly described here in this review.

4.1. Magnetic properties :

Transition metals and inner transition metals both exhibit magnetic property due to presence at least single unpaired electron. But other factors such as spin orbital coupling, deviation from regular complex structure, nature of ligand and surrounded solvent system vanish the magnetism. The good choice of metal containing cation or anion with their counterion will help to protect the magnetism. However, this magnetism will differ from other magnetic materials. M-ILs which shows response to the external magnetic field are known as magnetic ILs or paramagnetic ILs (Fig. 7).

These possess magnetic properties by itself without any need for the addition of magnetic nanoparticles to ILs. So they act as a molecular magnet. Their paramagnetic property originate either from the anion or cation or from both of them depending on the metal ion location. This new class of magnetic fluids has been synthesized as an attempt to develop inherent magnetic property in ILs and has progressively contributed to the research field of 'magnetism in

Fig. 6. Electrospray ionization mass spectrometry (ESI-MS) of the metal-containing anions, $[\text{CuCl}_2\text{Br}]^-$, $[\text{FeCl}_3\text{Br}]^-$, and $[\text{ZnCl}_2\text{Br}]^-$, coordinated in ionic liquids (Fig. reproduced from Ref. 13, Copyright to ACS, 2017).

Fig. 7. Response of the orange-colored ionic liquid 1 to a neodymium magnet (Fig. reproduced from Ref. 23, Copyright to Wiley, 2008).

liquids'. These single-component ILs are magnetic nanoparticle-free unlike ferrofluids, but usually consist of complexes of magnetic ions with high magnetic moment.

Paramagnetic ILs have some additional major advantages of over other conventional magnetic fluids such as ferrofluids and magnetorheological fluids as a consequence of their optical transparency, small-line width and high color purity, easy to handle which makes them more suitable for many potential optical and magnetic applications¹⁴. Usually, due to magnetic property and high boiling point, possibility of magnetic separation and recycling can be considered as comparatively greener process. Incorporating different types of magnetic metal anions in ILs cause its strong sensitivity to magnetic field which creates in them an additional advantage of its recoverability and reuse¹⁵.

All transition metal based ILs with unpaired number have exhibited paramagnetic behavior at room temperature. The magnetic susceptibilities of these has been measured using a Quantum Design superconducting quantum interference device (SQUID)¹⁶. The transition metal based ILs display simple paramagnetic behavior over the temperature range of 50–350 K, and room temperature magnetic susceptibility values (χ_T) has been found well corresponding with their respective spin states¹⁷. The magnetic susceptibility measurements have been considered to measure the degree of magnetization of MILs containing different transition metals in their structure in response to an applied external magnetic field quantitatively. The magnetic susceptibility of most of these ILs has been measured at room temperature with sweep of magnetic field range (kOe).

The straight line obtained between the magnetic

Fig. 8. Magnetization of Co, Mn, Fe and Gd based PMILs with the function of magnetic field at 300 K (Fig. reproduced from Ref. 19, Copyright to Wiley, 2017).

susceptibility and the applied magnetic field indicates the paramagnetic behaviour (Fig. 8). The linear fitting of that straight line gives quantitative values of magnetic susceptibility¹⁸. The values from various magnetic ILs has been listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Magnetic susceptibility of the PMILs (Copyright © 2012 Royal Society of Chemistry (From Ref. 18))

Anion	Cation	Magnetic susceptibility/ χ_{mT} (emu K.mol ⁻¹)
[CoCl ₄]	[P _{6,6,6,14}]	2.10/2.48
[Co(NCS) ₄]	[P _{6,6,6,14}]	2.06
[MnCl ₄]	[P _{6,6,6,14}]	4.23/4.22
[FeCl ₄]	[P _{6,6,6,14}]	4.29/4.34/4.05
[FeCl ₄]	[C ₂ mim]	4.03
[FeCl ₄]	[C ₄ mim]	4.11
[FeCl ₄]	[C ₄ py]	4.34
[GdCl ₆]	[P _{6,6,6,14}]	6.51/7.72
[Dy(SCN) _{8-x} (H ₂ O) _x], (X=0–2)	[C ₆ mim]	13.41–14.00

4.2. Luminescent properties :

Some lanthanide metals like Eu, Sm, Tb and Yb shows luminescent property. Lanthanide mostly used in form of their complex. Lanthanide complexes have exceptional optical properties compared to traditional organic dyes such as large Stokes shifts, long luminescence lifetimes (μ s–ms) and sharp emission peaks¹⁹. In 2006, Peter Nockemann for the first time reported the series of rare earth metal lanthanide from Ln to

Yb based ILs $[C_4mim]_{x-3}[Ln(NCS)_x(H_2O)_y]$, ($x = 6-8$, $y = 0-2$, $Ln = Y, La, Pr, Nd, Sm, Eu, Gd, Tb, Ho, Er$ and Yb)²⁰.

The first europium based IL was prepared by Koen Binnemans *et al.* in 2006, and that is 1-hexyl-3-methylimidazolium tetrakis(naphthoyltrifluoroacetato)europate(III) (Fig. 9). The luminescent ionogel was formed from this IL by using silica gel network²¹.

Fig. 9. Luminescence of europium(III)-doped ionogel under ultraviolet irradiation (Fig. reproduced from Ref. 22 with permission, Copyright 2006, American Chemical Society).

In 2008, Anja-Verena Mudring *et al.* further disclosed the NTf_2 based ILs with low melting point, $[R]_x[Eu(Tf_2N)_{3+x}]$ (where, $Tf_2N = \text{bis}-(\text{trifluoromethanesulfonyl})$ amide; $x = 1$ for $R = 1\text{-propyl-3-methylimidazolium}$ (C_3mim) and $1\text{-butyl-3-methylimidazolium}$ (C_4mim); $x = 2$ for $R = 1\text{-butyl-1-methylpyrrolidinium}$ (C_4mpyr))²². After Eu based IL, in 2008, Anja-Verena Mudring further reported the Dy based IL which have magnetic as well as luminescent properties. They synthesized the new ILs $[C_6mim]_{5-x}[Dy(SCN)_{8-x}(H_2O)_x]$ ($x = 0-2$, $C_6mim = 1\text{-hexyl-3-methylimidazolium}$) from $[C_6mim]SCN$, $KSCN$, and $Dy(ClO_4)_3 \cdot 6H_2O$ ²³. Fig. 10 shows the spectral transition during emission.

In 2009, Koen Binnemans reviewed the various lanthanide complex based hybrid materials including OLED and LASER applications²⁴. Uday Maitra *et al.* have prepared luminescent ionogel using

Fig. 10. Emission spectra of Dy^{III} based ionic liquid with transition assignment of the compounds $[C_6mim]_3[Dy(SCN)_6(H_2O)_2]$ (green), $[C_6mim]_4[Dy(SCN)_7(H_2O)]$ (red), and $[C_6mim]_5[Dy(SCN)_8]$ (black) at room temperature under excitation at $\lambda_{ex} = 453$ nm (Fig. reproduced from Ref. 23, Copyright to 2008, Wiley-VCH Verlag GmbH & Co. KGaA, Weinheim).

europiumcholate IL in 2010 and studied the luminescent nature of ionogel. They have demonstrated the role of pyrene in luminescent enhancement where pyrene transferred the energy to the singlet excited state (S_1). Fig. 11 shows the time-delayed emission spectra of Eu-cholate gel (5 mM/15 mM) in the pres-

Fig. 11. Time-delayed emission spectra of Eu-cholate gel (5 mM/15 mM) in the presence of pyrene when excited at 335 nm; delay time 0.2 ms; gate time 3 ms (Reproduced from Ref. 26, Copyright to the Royal Society of Chemistry, 2010).

ence of pyrene²⁵. Auhors also prepared other lanthanide cholate based ionogels and characterized them in this study²⁶.

In 2010, Slawomir Pitula and Anja-Verena Mudring demonstrated the luminescent nature of d block transition metal Mn with Cl and NTf₂ anion. Figs. 12 and 13 shows the luminescent nature of these Mn^{II} based ILs⁸.

4.3. Catalytic properties :

Now various ionic liquids have been prepared for organic transformation by taking advantage of versatile properties such as low vapour pressure, high boiling point, easy to recovery, and reusability. Most of

Fig. 12. Emission spectra of [C₂mim]₂[MnCl₄] (top) and [C₂mim][Mn(Tf₂N)₃] (bottom) (Reproduced from Ref. 8, Copyright to 2010, Wiley-VCH Verlag GmbH and Co. KGaA, Weinheim).

Fig. 13. From left to right in the top row [C₂mim]₂[MnCl₄], [C₃mim]₂[MnCl₄], [C₄mim]₂[MnCl₄], and [C₆mim]₂[MnCl₄]; in the bottom row [C₂mim][Mn(Tf₂N)₃], [C₃mim][Mn(Tf₂N)₃], [C₄mim][Mn(Tf₂N)₃], and [C₆mim][Mn(Tf₂N)₃] excited at room temperature with UV light ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 366 \text{ nm}$) (Reproduced from Ref. 8, Copyright to 2010, Wiley-VCH Verlag GmbH and Co. KGaA, Weinheim).

the transition and inner transition metals has been used for various industrially important organic transformations. The synergic effect has been uncovered when incorporation such metals is considered in IL properties. The additional feature like magnetic character has been used, for example, in easy separation of products from the reaction mixture and removal of catalyst at the end of reaction. Since iron is one of the most inexpensive metal among transition metals, the scope for iron-catalyzed organic reactions is of great interest and constantly growing. All of these features open a new frontier of reinventing organic reactions practiced in chemical industry leading to improved process performance. M-ILs have been used in chemical reactions in form of catalyst or reaction medium.

In 2001, Valkenberg *et al.* investigated the cata-

lytic use of $[\text{FeCl}_4]^-$ anion based IL in the Friedel-Crafts acylation of aromatic compounds as an alternative to existing homogeneous catalysts²⁷.

Fig. 14. Chitosan supported magnetic ionic liquid as a catalyst²⁸ (Fig. reproduced from Ref. 28, Copyright to RSC Advances, 2014).

In 2013, Muraoka *et al.* first time reported an effective utilization of M-ILs as a medium in dissolution of crystalline cellulose and recovery of cellulose magnetically²⁹. More details are described in this review under application section.

4.4. Electrochemical properties :

The accessibility of variable oxidation state in transition metals allow to use them in electrochemical application. M-ILs have been disclosed as new electrochromic materials for the manufacturing of different electronic devices such as information displays, anti-glare rear view of automobiles, smart windows, etc. by taking advantage of photophysical and optical properties that originate from the various metals incorporated in the complex anion of corresponding IL. In 2011, Luis C. Branco and Fernando Pinaet *et al.* proposed Co, Cr and Fe based ILs are not only capable of behaving as electrolytes but also to make an electrochromic component. The appropriate combination of electrochromic and magnetic anions make them suitable candidate for electrochemical applications. They have also proved that anions or cations which have metal with variable oxidation nature are capable of reversible oxidation/reduction processes involving the strong changes in either colour or their

magnetic properties and even in both. They prepared the novel electrochromic and magnetic ILs (Fig. 15) by a simple combination of Co^{III} , Cr^{III} and Fe^{III} with ethylenediaminetetraacetic (EDTA) complexes as anions and the cations was used 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium [C_2mim], 1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium [C_4mim], 1-octyl-3-methylimidazolium [C_4mim], trioctylmethylammonium [N_{1888}] and trihexyltetradecylphosphonium [$\text{P}_{6,6,6,14}$]³⁰.

Fig. 15. Visible variations of the compound [C_2mim][$\text{Co}(\text{EDTA})$] upon reduction at -0.38 V and 300 min. A liquid U shaped electrochromic cell containing two immiscible ionic liquids showing simultaneous oxidation reduction (Reproduced from Ref. 30, Copyright to The Royal Society of Chemistry, 2011).

Akitsu and Einaga *et al.* in 2006, reported a new photo-controllable supramolecular system containing [C_4mim][FeCl_4] and azobenzene as a new photo-functional magnetic material with application for memory devices³¹.

4.5. Thermo and solvatochromism :

Some of the M-ILs investigated showed thermochromic as well as solvatochromic properties. In 2008, George Z. Chen *et al.* prepared chloro-Ni^{II} complexes based ILs. Thermochromic and solvatochromic behaviour was investigated by visual observation and visible-spectroscopy in 1-hydroxyalkyl-3-methylimidazolium [C_n(OH)mim][ClO₄], where n = 2 or 3 based ionic liquid in the range of 25 to 85 °C. The hypothesis was given by them that the tetrahedral [NiCl₄]⁻ (blue, hot) has been converted into octahedral structure [NiCl_x(C_n(OH)mim)_y]^{z+} (yellow or green, cold) upon where [C_n(OH)mim]⁺ cation IL has been used as ligand.

Fig. 16 shows that colour of [C₄mim][NiCl₄] is changed upon heating due to evaporation of ethanol where [C₄mim]Cl stabilized the colour intensity. Fig. 16 also confirmed the importance of hydroxyl group which utilized in coordination bonding with Ni metal ion³².

Fig. 16. Photos of [C₄mim]₂[NiCl₄] in ethanol and [C₃(OH)mim]BF₄ at the indicated temperatures (Reproduced from Ref. 32, Copyright to The Royal Society of Chemistry, 2008).

In 2014, again George Z. Chen *et al.* disclosed the Cryo-solvatochromism. The Cryo-solvatochromism is more precise term of thermochromism along with solvatochromism. Blue to green colour changes in response to cooling from room temperature to well below 0 °C can have many applications. The Cryo-solvatochromism of di-(1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium)

tetrachloro-nickelate [C₄mim]₂[NiCl₄] and excess of 1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium chloride [C₄mim]Cl has been demonstrated by George Z. Chen in an IL solvent, 1-(2-hydroxyethyl)-3-methylimidazolium tetrafluoroborate [C₂(OH)mim]BF₄ (Fig. 17)³³.

Fig. 17. Photographs of 0.14 mole.L⁻¹ [C₄mim]₂[NiCl₄] and 1.4 mole.L⁻¹ [C₄mim]Cl in [C₂(OH)mim]BF₄ at (A) 22 °C and (B) -13 °C (Reproduced from Ref. 33, Copyright to The Royal Society of Chemistry, 2014).

In 2016, Jun Ding and Xianmao Lu *et al.* have reported for the first time the thermoresponsive Fe based magnetic ILs octyltrimethylammonium bromotrichloroferrate(III) ([N_{1,1,1,8}][FeBrCl₃]), dodecyltrimethylammonium tetrachloroferrate(III) ([N_{1,1,1,12}][FeCl₄]), tetradecyltrimethylammonium bromotrichloroferrate(III) ([N_{1,1,1,14}][FeBrCl₃]), and 8-butyl-1,8-diazabicyclo[5.4.0]undec-7-ene bromotrichloroferrate(III) ([DBU-Bu][FeBrCl₃]). All four magnetic ILs respond to temperature change. They have investigated the thermoresponsive behaviour of magnetic ILs (25 wt%) using UV-Vis transmittance at 600 nm with temperature. Fig. 18 shows the lower critical solution temperature (LCST) of [N_{1,1,1,8}][FeCl₄] and [DBU-Bu][FeBrCl₃] are 60 °C and 50 °C respectively, at which the % transmittances dropped abruptly (LCST is the critical temperature below which the components of a mixture are miscible for all compositions).

The concentration of magnetic ILs also interfere in the lowering of LCST. The LCST of [N_{1,1,1,8}][FeCl₄] was reduced from 60 to 38 °C when concentration changed from 25 to 33 wt%. Similarly for [DBU-Bu][FeBrCl₃] the LCSTs were 63 and 50 °C at concentrations of 20 wt% and 25 wt% respectively³⁴.

Fig. 18. (a) Change in UV-Vis transmittance with temperature at 25% wt. (b) Change in UV-Vis transmittance with temperature at different concentrations. Heating of [DBU-Bu][FeBrCl₃] solution from 24 to 50 °C and magnetic separation from water at 50 °C (Reproduced from Ref. 34, Copyright to The Royal Society of Chemistry, 2016).

5. Applications

5.1. Catalysis :

As described in the Section 4.3 M-ILs have been used in various organic transformation. M-ILs have been used either in form of catalyst or medium. In 2005, Andrew P. Abbott *et al.* investigated the use of zinc-based IL which was prepared by mixing of 1 eq. of choline chloride and 2 eq. of ZnCl₂; [ChCl][ZnCl₂]₂ for the O-acetylation of sugars and cellulose³⁵. Here [ChCl][ZnCl₂]₂ played the role of solvent as well as catalyst. In 2005, Donghong Yin *et al.* prepared diphenylmethane and its derivatives via Friedel-Crafts benzylation reaction where 1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium chloride-ZnCl₂ ([C₄mim]Cl-ZnCl₂), 1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium chloride-FeCl₃ ([C₄mim]Cl-FeCl₃) and 1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium chloride-FeCl₂ ([C₄mim]Cl-FeCl₂) were used both reaction media and Lewis acid catalysts. These ILs were conveniently recovered and for recycled. [C₄mim]Cl-ZnCl₂ was reused at least eight times without loss of catalytic activity due to higher moisture³⁶. In 2008, Bica *et al.* developed the very efficient, easily prepared and reusable iron-containing IL; butylmethylimidazolium tetrachloroferrate(III) [C₄mim][FeCl₄] as a coherent and magnetic catalyst

for the hydromethylation of the β-keto ester in high yield. They also investigated the other transition metals Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Cu^{II} and Ti^{IV} for desired reactions³⁷. In 2010, Yu Lin Hu *et al.* have reported the conversion of benzyl chloride and its derivative to benzaldehyde using surface active magnetic IL [C₁₂mim][FeCl₄] with oxidant H₅IO₆. [C₁₂mim][FeCl₄] demonstrated the best performance. Authors also investigated the catalytic effects of other different alkyl chain containing magnetic ILs which may be attributed to their different abilities of stabilizing and dissolving H₅IO₆ and the substrate. Under similar reaction conditions, H₅IO₆ was more soluble in [C₁₂mim][FeCl₄], leading to higher effective concentration of the oxidant³⁸. In same year 2010, Hui Wang *et al.* have showed the high synergic effect and eco-friendly approach for the glycolysis of the PET plastic by using the [C₄mim][FeCl₄] as an efficient catalyst in ethylene glycol medium³⁹. In continuation to degrade PET plastic, Hui Wang *et al.* 2015, further investigated the high selectivity and recyclability of first transition metal based IL¹². Amutha Chinnappan *et al.* 2013, proposed the nanocomposite supported catalytic reduction of nitroarenes. The nanocomposite was prepared from PVDF with nickel-based dicationic IL,

$[C_6(\text{mpy})_2][NiCl_4]^{2-}$ at room temperature. The polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF)-Ni based nanofiber composite catalyst was proposed more active than other Ni-based catalysts. The use of such nanofiber eliminated the need of inert atmosphere, and additional base or other additives. The catalytic system showed the good yields and selectivity (Fig. 19)⁴⁰.

Fig. 19. Reduction of aromatic nitro compounds to the corresponding aniline with $[C_6(\text{mpy})_2][NiCl_4]$, $NaBH_4$ and H_2O (Reproduced from Ref. 40, Copyright to The Royal Society of Chemistry, 2013).

In 2014, Soheil Sayyahi *et al.* prepared paramagnetic 3-(2-hydroxyethyl)-1-methyl imidazolium bromotrichloro ferrate(III) $[C_2(\text{OH})\text{mim}][FeCl_3Br]$ which was used in the catalytic synthesis of 1-amidoalkyl-2-naphthols via one-pot three-component condensation reaction of aromatic aldehydes, 2-naphthol and acetamide at 85 °C under solvent-free conditions⁴¹. In 2014, Ali Khalafi-Nezhad *et al.* proposed a green and highly efficient chitosan supported magnetic IL (CSMIL, Fig. 14) which was synthesized from chitosan, methyl imidazole and anhydrous/hydrous $FeCl_3$ ²⁸. The heterogeneous catalyst thus obtained was used for the direct conversion of aldehydes to the corresponding nitriles in the presence of $NH_2OH.HCl$ /dry-CSMIL/ $MeSO_2Cl$ and amides with $NH_2OH.HCl$ /wet-CSMIL/ $MeSO_2Cl$ ²⁸. In 2015, AliAkbari developed an efficient green catalyst for the one-pot synthesis of 1,2,4,5-tetrasubstituted imidazoles via the condensation of benzil, an aromatic aldehyde, aniline and ammonium acetate. The green salt and magnetic gadolinium-based IL, $[C_4\text{mim}]_3[GdCl_6]$ was used for this reaction (Fig. 20)⁴².

Further in series of condensation reactions, in 2015, Soheil Sayyahi *et al.* used $[Bmim][FeCl_4]$ as a catalyst for a synthesis of 2-aryl benzimidazoles and 2-aryl benzothiazoles derivatives with high yield⁴³. In

Fig. 20. Reaction scheme (Reproduced from Ref. 42, Copyright to *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2016).

2015, Lei Yang *et al.* also carried out catalytic reaction from dual magnetic ionic liquid-mesoporous silica. The mesoporous silica was synthesised from M-IL, $[C_{16}\text{mim}]_3\text{PMo}_{12}\text{O}_{40}$ and the triblock copolymer P123 as co-templates. In this strategy, the IL, $[C_{16}\text{mim}]_3\text{PMo}_{12}\text{O}_{40}$ was not only employed as the template, but also provided the metal source. Dual magnetic IL-mesoporous silica has been used as a catalyst for the oxidative desulfurization of fuel⁴⁴. Maren Muntzeck *et al.* 2016, proposed a three-component oxidative dehydrogenation tandem reaction via the coupling and hydroarylation of benzaldehyde, aniline and phenylacetylene to a quinoline derivative which was catalysed by an iron-containing IL with anions $[FeCl_4]^-$ and $[Fe_2Cl_7]^-$ ⁴⁵. In 2017, Huiqing Liu *et al.* showed the excellent catalytic activity of the magnetic ionic liquid $[C_4\text{mim}][FeCl_4]$ for methanolysis of poly(lactic acid)⁴⁶. Recently Sachin R. Thawarkar *et al.* 2017, have synthesized imidazolium based nickel and palladium containing catalyst $[C_4\text{mim}]_2[PdCl_4]$ and $[C_4\text{mim}]_2[NiCl_4]$ and used as effective catalysts for the reduction of nitroarenes to aminoarenes in the presence of $NaBH_4$. The catalytic enhancement was attributed to *in situ* formation of Pd and Ni metal nanoparticles (NPs) were formed by the reduction of respective M-ILs⁴⁷.

5.2. Biomass processing :

The depletion of conventional fuels is forcing mankind to focus on renewable sources for the production of energy, fuels and chemicals⁴⁸. Biomass is the one of the renewable sources of conventional fuels. Hence, it is very important to utilize this biomass for its valorization into a basic building block compound. On the other hand cost of such chemicals has increased and availability is decreased⁴⁹. Use of ILs as solvents in biomass dissolution and conversion of dis-

solved biomass fractions like lignin into chemicals is promising⁵⁰.

Specially IL as solvent and metal chloride as a catalyst is being used widely for this type of biomass⁵¹. The use metal containing ILs for this application plays dual functions viz. as solvent and as a catalyst. There are very few reports available where ILs have been used as both the solvent and catalyst for biomass processing. The first report of conversion of biomass into other chemicals was reported by Liang *et al.*, where they used IL $[\text{Et}_3\text{NH}]\text{Cl}-\text{AlCl}_3$ along with other ILs and converted soybean oil into biodiesel. They have studied different variation of ILs along with $[\text{Et}_3\text{NH}]\text{Cl}$ in conjugation with metal chlorides like Fe, Zn, Mg and Sn. They also studied effect of different anions on conversion of soybean oil into biodiesel⁵². In 2013, Muraoka *et al.* successfully dissolved crystalline cellulose using magnetic IL, $[\text{C}_m\text{mim}]\text{FeCl}_4$. They concluded that cationic moiety may play major role behind dissolution of cellulose²⁹. The another report by Saidana *et al.* states the conversion of oil palm fronds (OPF) into levulinic acid (Fig. 21). They used acidic ionic liquid $[\text{SMIM}]\text{FeCl}_4$ to convert OPF and glucose into levulinic acid. They also achieved up gradation of levulinic acid to ethyl levulinate through esterification with ethanol over $[\text{SMIM}]\text{FeCl}_4$ ⁵³.

5.3. Magnetic surfactants and their colloidal formulations :

There is a vast possibility of tuning the IL structures and it is well known that amphiphilic character

can be introduced in ILs by incorporating long alkyl chains to IL moieties. These compounds are structural relatives of common surfactants and have been coined surfactant ionic liquids (SAILs). Recently, surfactants responsive to a magnetic field have been developed that offer unique physicochemical properties. The surfactants those shows response toward external magnetic field are identified as Magnetic Ionic Liquid Surfactants (MILSs, Fig. 21). In 2012, Julian Eastoe *et al.* showed that MILSs can be readily produced by mixing an iron trihalide with the appropriate cationic surfactant. Surprisingly, even micellar solutions of these MILSs demonstrate a field response, leading to the intriguing possibility of micellar structuring, which would not happen with a normal non-micellizing magnetic IL⁵⁴. In continuation 2013, the group of Paul Brown and Julian Eastoe further prepared another kind of MILs which included lanthanides metal counterions (Ho, Gd and Ce) also and characterized well⁵⁵. Heteroanions containing MILs have been developed from same group where $[\text{FeCl}_3\text{Br}]$ and $[\text{AOT}]$ anions has been used simultaneously. Sebastian Polarz *et al.* reported that aqueous phase behaviour of MILSs is similar to that of conventional surfactants and self-assembly provides a simple means of preparing well-defined aggregates of metal complexes related magnetic surfactant⁵⁶.

This discovery adds to the armoury of responsive stimuli, allowing for surfactant properties to be controlled simply by the switching “on” and “off” of a magnetic field. SQUID magnetometry has been used

Fig. 21. Conversion of OPF to HMF and LA (Work is reproduced from Ref. 53, Copy right to Springer Science +Business Media, New York, 2016).

Fig. 22. Response of liquid droplets to the field from a 0.4 T NdFeB magnet. [$C_{10}mimCl$] and [$C_{10}mimF$] = 20 wt% (Reproduced from Ref. 54)⁵⁴.

to elucidate the magnetic phase behavior, and small-angle neutron scattering (SANS) provides evidence of micellar aggregation in aqueous media. The study also reveals that for cationic surfactants in aqueous systems there appears to be no significant increase in magnetic susceptibility after micellization⁵⁵. In 2016, Paul Brown *et al.* used muon spin relaxation spectroscopy to study how the aggregation behavior of magnetic surfactants containing lanthanide counterions may be exploited to create spin glass-like materials. The magnetic behavior of MILs may also be manipulated via formation of micelles rather than simple dilution as well as via design of surfactant molecular architecture⁵⁷. Metal-based ILs have also been used to construct microemulsions (MEs) and other colloidal formulations. It is well known, MEs are the thermodynamically stable clear transparent solutions consisting of polar, nonpolar and an emulsifier. The part of review has focused on MEs which have utilized metal based ILs or DES as required components^{58–60}.

Introduction of metal based ILs to MEs leads to wider applications, especially for the synthesis of nano-materials based on their magnetic nature.

MEs formed from magnetic ILs are rarely found, and has limited reports till date. MEs with magnetic properties has been formed by employing a magnetic

room temperature ionic liquid i.e. [C_4mim][$FeCl_4$] as polar phase, cyclohexane as non-polar phase and an appropriate mixture of ionic surfactant and decanol as a cosurfactant (Fig. 23)⁶¹.

When the alkyl chain length of the imidazolium moiety is increased to C_{10} , the IL, 1-methyl-3-

Fig. 23. (a) Response of the MRTIL containing MEs to the field gradient of an electromagnet. The sample shown consists of 31.2 wt% D12-cyclohexane, 46.1 wt% $bmim[FeCl_4]$, 11.8 wt% $C_{16}mimCl$ and 10.9 wt% decanol. The magnetic field is oriented parallel to the liquid surface. (b) Pseudo ternary phase diagram (by weight) for mixtures of MRTIL ($bmim[FeCl_4]$) and cyclohexane formulated with $C_{16}mimCl$ and decanol (molar ratio 1 : 2) as surfactant and co-surfactant, respectively. The filled squares mark the detected phase transitions and the filled circles indicate the SANS samples. The dashed line gives the experimental path for conductivity titration and magnetic measurements (Reproduced from Ref. 61, Copyright to The Royal Society of Chemistry, 2012).

decylimidazolium tetrachloroferrate ($[C_{10}mim][FeCl_4]$) proved to be surface active and generated a magnetic ionic liquid surfactant (MILS)⁵⁴.

Ammonium and imidazolium based magnetic surfactants have been studied for their aggregation behaviour using SANS technique by Eastoe and co-workers⁵⁵.

The opinion on aggregation of magnetic surfactants has been provided by Brown *et al.*⁶².

5.4. Material synthesis :

From past to present, studies on nanomaterials have played key role in applied science. Requirement of these materials is high due to their high surface area, low size and desired physicochemical properties. Synthesis of these advanced materials (functional materials, quantum dots, porous materials etc.) using greener methods is desired. Among such methods, utilization of IL based MEs as “Nano reactors” is very promising^{63,64}.

Scheme below provides an overview of how the NPs are synthesized in a cyclic manner using IL based MEs (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1. General synthetic route for the preparation of nanoparticles (NPs) using magnetic based MEs.

Inclusion of metal based ILs for the synthesis of nanoparticles in an eco-friendly manner is very important. Xiong *et al.* have reported highly mesoporous materials for the first time wherein various metal-

containing mesoporous silica materials were synthesized by using different M-ILs, ($[C_{16}mim]Cl/CuCl_2$, $[C_{16}mim]Cl/FeCl_3$, $[C_{16}mim]Cl/MnCl_2$ and $[C_{16}mim]Cl/NiCl_2$ as templates, tetraethyl orthosilicate (TEOS) as silica source at room temperature in acidic media (Fig. 24)⁶⁵.

Fig. 24. The formation process of the metal-containing mesoporous silica⁶⁵ (Copyright Ref. 65 to Royal Society of Chemistry, 2014).

In this review, magnetic ILs (as polar, nonpolar and as an emulsifier or template) based MEs have been focussed and explored huge advantages of such MEs to produce single distributed ultra-fine preferred size and morphologies, and properties in eco-friendly manner.

Following are the advantages of M-ILs based MEs :

- (1) It is an eco-friendly method such as recyclable “Nanoreactors”.
- (2) Single distribution in size.
- (3) Desired morphological materials (spherical, rod etc.).
- (4) Inducing magnetic nature (for desired applications).

(5) Regeneration of M-ILs based MEs.

Limitations of M-ILs based MEs :

(1) M-ILs are somewhat costly materials compared to conventional solvents.

(2) Some of M-ILs are toxic in nature.

5.5. Extraction and stability of biomolecules :

ILs have been used to resolve the major challenges in biotechnology including effective control over transport and delivery of biomolecules for the regulation of gene suppression, targeted drug delivery⁶⁶, and protein separation⁶⁷. In 2012, Paul Brown *et al.* demonstrated the unprecedented low strength magnetic field-induced migration of DNA and proteins (biomolecules separation) via magnetic surfactant conjugation. Moreover, near-native conformations of the biomolecules could be maintained by careful control over the biomolecule : surfactant stoichiometry. They have used magnetic cationic surfactants DTAF ($[\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{34}\text{N}]^+[\text{FeCl}_3\text{Br}]^-$), DTAG ($[\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{34}\text{N}]^+[\text{GdCl}_3\text{Br}]^-$) and DTAH ($[\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{34}\text{N}]^+[\text{HoCl}_3\text{Br}]^-$) for this study⁶⁸. In 2015, Jingcheng Hao *et al.* reported a low strength magnetic field-induced migration of DNA and proteins via the conjunction with one kind of novel surfactant-coated magnetic AuNP (Fig. 25). The advantage of using these nanoparticles is their easy preparation (one-step modification), good stability and dispersibility, fast and effective binding, and high migration efficiency. The native conformation of DNA and proteins can be protected during the migration process by carefully controlling the stoichiometric ratio of the AuNPs and biomolecules⁶⁹.

Further, in biotechnology magnetic extraction phases have been employed in nucleic acid analysis as mobile substrates for the rapid extraction of DNA. In magnet-based approaches, the DNA-enriched extraction medium is readily isolated and controlled by application of an external magnetic field. Functionalized magnetic beads are commonly used in forensics and drug discovery applications to increase sample throughput by eliminating the need for tedious centrifugation steps⁷⁰. In 2015, Jared L. Anderson *et al.* have studied extraction of DNA using hydrophobic M-ILs. In total, three hydrophobic M-ILs, namely 1,12-bis[N-(N'-hexadecylbenzimidazolium)-dodecane

Fig. 25. Synthesis of the magnetic gold particles and demonstration of migration (Reproduced from Ref. 69, Copyright to The Royal Society of Chemistry, 2015).

bis[(trifluoromethyl)sulfonyl] imide bromotrichloroferrate(III) ($[(\text{C}_{16}\text{BnIM})_2\text{C}_{12}^{2+}][\text{NTf}_2^-, \text{FeCl}_3\text{Br}^-]$), benzyltrioctylammonium bromotrichloroferrate(III) ($[(\text{C}_8)_3\text{BnN}^+][\text{FeCl}_3\text{Br}^-]$), and trihexyl(tetradecyl)-phosphonium tetra-chloroferrate(III) ($[\text{P}_{6,6,6,14}^+][\text{FeCl}_4^-]$), have been employed for the direct extraction of DNA from an aqueous solution (Fig. 26). They isolated the extraction phase by applying an external magnetic field, thereby circumventing time-consuming centrifugation steps.

The optimized M-ILs based extraction procedures are capable of performing rapid and highly efficient extraction of double-stranded and single-stranded DNA from a matrix containing metal ions and protein. Plasmid DNA (pDNA) has also been extracted from a bacterial cell lysate using the M-ILs based method and shown to be a high quality template for PCR⁷¹. In same year 2015 and same group Jared L. Anderson *et al.*, have been reported a method for M-ILs

Fig. 26. Reproduced the graphical abstract from Ref. 71.

based extraction of bacterial plasmid DNA (pDNA) followed by immediate PCR amplification and detection of a target gene (Fig. 27). They designed the PCR buffer to enable the amplification of a target gene from pDNA-enriched magnetic ionic liquids. According to them by carefully engineering the components within a PCR mixture, the pDNA-enriched M-IL could be added directly to a PCR tube for gene amplification without additional sample purification. The results have been demonstrated the feasibility of interfacing M-IL extraction solvents with biochemical assays to achieve rapid enrichment and analysis of DNA.

The results have also showed that PCR inhibition caused by the cationic and anionic components of two M-ILs; trihexyl(tetradecyl)phosphonium tetrachloroferrate(III) ($[P_{6,6,6,14}]^+ [FeCl_4]^-$) MIL or the trioctylbenzylammonium bromotrichloroferrate(III) ($[(C_8)_3BnN]^+ [FeCl_3Br]^-$) could be mitigated using albumin, iron(III) chelators and by increased buffer

capacity of the PCR mixture. These M-ILs were also used to extract PCR amplifiable pDNA from crude bacterial cell lysate without the need for time consuming sample purification or DNA recovery procedures. This study done by them opens up the compatibility of M-ILs solvents with bioanalytical techniques to dramatically reduce the time required for DNA analysis, making these materials particularly attractive for food safety or other high throughput applications⁶⁰. In 2015 Jingcheng Hao *et al.* have constructed for the first time well-ordered surfactant- DNA hybrid nanospheres made from double-strand DNA and cationic surfactants with magnetic counterion, $[FeCl_3Br]^-$. The magnetic cationic surfactants compacted the DNA at high concentrations and built well-ordered nanospheres through aggregation, fusion, and coagulation processes. They also used light-responsive magnetic cationic surfactant to produce nanospheres which was further used as a dual controllable drug-delivery system. These systems can be stimulated with external magnetic force and alternative UV and visible light (Fig. 28). The formed nanospheres had high drug absorption efficiency, slow release property, and good biocompatibility. Authors explored the potential candidates for effective magnetic-field-based targeted drug delivery, followed by photocontrollable drug release⁷².

Conclusion and Future Visions

In this review, the main focus have been centred to the synthesis, characterization and applications of metal based ionic liquids (M-ILs). M-ILs containing tran-

Fig. 27. Amplification of the MTAP gene within PCR buffers spiked with (a) 20 mM $FeCl_3$, (b) 0.5 mL of $[(C_8)_3BnN]^+ [Br]^-$ (lane 3) or 0.5 mL of $[P_{6,6,6,14}]^+ [Cl]^-$ (lanes 4–6).

Fig. 28. UV-Visible and magnetic field triggered drug delivery by using magnetic surfactant (Reprinted from Ref. 72, Copyright to 2015, American Chemical Society).

sition metals like Co, Cr, V, Mn, Fe, Cu, Ni and the lanthanide complexes Gd, Ho, Yb, Tb and Dy have been studied and explored for their potential applications. Special properties of M-ILs such optical or luminescence, magnetic and catalytic are leading to new interesting potential applications in both process and product engineering. Regarding process engineering, M-ILs may be applied in extraction, separation and as hydrophobic media. In chemical reactions they can act as catalyst, solvent or reaction medium. With reference to product engineering, M-ILs can be used in applications related to the polymer chemistry, development of electrochemical and medical devices. Biotechnological and biomedical applications are also linked with M-ILs. Many other important applications in fields such as microextraction, environmental remediation and gas adsorption possess great synthetic importance. Utility of certain paramagnetic ILs as promising candidates for CO₂ gas adsorption needs to be given special attention because of the growing concern for global warming and other related causes.

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Chemical Society for providing the opportunity to submit the review on metal based ionic liquids.

Abbreviation :

ILs	Ionic liquids
[PF ₆] ⁻	Hexa fluorophosphate
[NTf ₂] ⁻	Bis trifluorosulfoamide
Cl ⁻	Chloride
Br ⁻	Bromide
Aliquat	
[CN] ⁻	Cyanide
NMR	Nuclear Magnetic Resonance
IR-	Infrared red
MS	Mass spectra
[FeCl ₄] ⁻	Tetrachloroferrate(III)
[MnCl ₄] ²⁻	Tetrachloromaganate(II)
[CuCl ₄] ²⁻	Tetrachlorocuparte(II)
[NiCl ₄] ²⁻	Tetrachloronickelate(II)
[CoCl ₄] ²⁻	Tetrachlorocobaltate(II)
[FeCl ₃ Br] ⁻	Bromotrichloroferrate(III)
[CuCl ₂ Br] ⁻	Bromodichlorocuprate(II)
[ZnCl ₂ Br] ⁻	Bromodichlorozincate(II)
DEA	Diethyl ammonium
ESI	Electron spray ionization
<i>m/z</i>	Mass to charge ratio
MILs	Magnetic ionic liquids
PMILs	Paramagnetic ionic liquid
SQUID	Superconducting quantum interface device
KOe	Kilo Oersteds
EDTA	Ethyldiamine tetraacetic acid
LCST	Lower critical solution temperature
ChCl	Choline chloride
PET	Polyethylene tetraphthalate
PVDF	Polyvinylidene fluoride
MILSs	Magnetic ionic liquid surfactants
SANS	Small-angle neutron scattering

Arvind Kumar *et al.* : Metal-based ionic liquids : Their properties, applications and future prospects

MEs	Micro-emulsions
DES	Deep eutectic solvent
MRTILs	Magnetic room temperature ionic liquid
DTAB	Dodecyl trimethylammonium-bromide
NPs	Nanoparticles
TEOS	Tetraethylorthosilicates
pDNA	plasmid DNA
PCR	Polymerase chain reaction

References

- L. Bai, J.-X. Wang and Y. Zhang, *Green Chem.*, 2003, **5**, 615.
- V. S. Padalkar, V. D. Gupta, K. R. Phatangare, V. S. Patil, P. G. Umape and N. Sekar, *Green Chem. Lett. Rev.*, 2012, **5**, 139.
- J. S. Wilkes, J. A. Levisky, R. A. Wilson and C. L. Hussey, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1982, **21**, 1263.
- F. Endres and S. Z. El-Abedin, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.*, 2006, **8**, 2101.
- E. Moustafa, S. Zein El-Abedin, A. Shkurankov, E. Zschippang, A. Saad, A. Bund and F. Endres, *J. Phys. Chem. (B)*, 2007, **111**, 4693.
- Z. Fei, T. J. Geldbach, D. Zhao and P. J. Dyson, *Chemistry-A European Journal*, 2006, **12**, 2122; R. P. Singh, R. D. Verma, D. T. Meshri and J. n. M. Shreeve, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2006, **45**, 3584; M. Smiglak, A. Metlen and R. D. Rogers, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 2007, **40**, 1182; W. L. Hough and R. D. Rogers, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 2007, **80**, 2262.
- H. Yu, J. Merib and J. L. Anderson, *J. Chromat. (A)*, 2016, **11**, 1463.
- S. Pitula and A. V. Mudring, *Chemistry-A European Journal*, 2010, **16**, 3355.
- F. A. Yassin, F. Y. El-Kady, H. S. Ahmed, L. K. Mohamed, S. A. Shaban and A. K. Elfadaly, *Egypt. J. Petro.*, 2015, **24**, 103.
- M. Döbbelin, V. Jovanovski, I. Llarena, L. J. C. Marfil, G. Cabañero, J. Rodriguez and D. Mecerreyes, *Polym. Chem.*, 2011, **2**, 1275.
- Y. Suffren, F.-G. Rollet and C. Reber, *Comm. Inorg. Chem.*, 2011, **32**, 246.
- Q. Wang, Y. Geng, X. Lu and S. Zhang, *ACS Sust. Chem. Eng.*, 2015, **3**, 340.
- Z. Zheng, J. Guo, H. Mao, Q. Xu, J. Qin and F. Yan, *ACS Biomat. Sci. Eng.*, 2017.
- J. Chen, "Application of Ionic Liquids on Rare Earth Green Separation and Utilization", Springer, 2015.
- S. H. Lee, S. H. Ha, C.-Y. You and Y.-M. Koo, *Korean J. Chem. Eng.*, 2007, **24**, 436.
- M. Li, S. L. De Rooy, D. K. Bwambok, B. El-Zahab, J. F. DiTusa and I. M. Warner, *Chem. Commun.*, 2009, 6922.
- R. E. Del Sesto, T. M. McCleskey, A. K. Burrell, G. A. Baker, J. D. Thompson, B. L. Scott, J. S. Wilkes and P. Williams, *Chem. Commun.*, 2008, 447.
- E. Santos, J. Albo, A. Rosatella, C. A. Afonso and Á. Irabien, *J. Chem. Technol. Biotech.*, 2014, **89**, 866.
- J.-C. G. Bünzli, *Chem. Rev.*, 2010, **110**, 2729.
- J. Alvarez-Vicente, S. Dandil, D. Banerjee, H. N. Gunaratne, S. Gray, S. Felton, G. Srinivasan, A. M. Kaczmarek, R. Van Deun and P. Nockemann, *J. Phys. Chem. (B)*, 2016, **120**, 5301.
- K. Lunstroot, K. Driesen, P. Nockemann, C. Görlner-Walrand, K. Binnemans, S. Bellayer, J. Le Bideau and A. Vioux, *Chem. Mater.*, 2006, **18**, 5711.
- S. Tang, A. Babai and A. V. Mudring, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2008, **47**, 7631.
- B. Mallick, B. Balke, C. Felser and A. V. Mudring, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2008, **47**, 7635.
- K. Binnemans, *Chem. Rev.*, 2009, **109**, 4283.
- S. Bhowmik, S. Banerjee and U. Maitra, *Chem. Commun.*, 2010, **46**, 8642.
- V. Sajisha and U. Maitra, *CHIMIA Int. J. Chem.*, 2013, **67**, 44.
- M. Valkenberg and W. Hölderich, *Green Chem.*, 2002, **4**, 88.
- A. Khalafi-Nezhad and S. Mohammadi, *RSC Adv.*, 2014, **4**, 13782.
- J. Muraoka, N. Kamiya and Y. Ito, *J. Mole. Liq.*, 2013, **182**, 76.
- A. Branco, L. C. Branco and F. Pina, *Chem. Commun.*, 2011, **47**, 2300.
- T. Akitsu and Y. Einaga, *Inorg. Chem. Commun.*, 2006, **9**, 1108.
- X. Wei, L. Yu, D. Wang, X. Jin and G. Z. Chen, *Green Chem.*, 2008, **10**, 296.
- L. Yu and G. Z. Chen, *RSC Adv.*, 2014, **4**, 40281.
- Q. Zhao, T. S. Heng, C. X. Guo, D. Zhao, J. Ding and X. Lu, *RSC Adv.*, 2016, **6**, 15731.
- A. P. Abbott, T. J. Bell, S. Handa and B. Stoddart, *Green Chem.*, 2005, **7**, 705.
- D. Yin, C. Li, L. Tao, N. Yu, S. Hu and D. Yin,

- J. Mole. Catal. A : Chem.*, 2006, **245**, 260.
37. K. Bica and P. Gaertner, *Eur. J. Org. Chem.*, 2008, 3453.
 38. Y. L. Hu, Q. F. Liu, T. T. Lu and M. Lu, *Catal. Commun.*, 2010, **11**, 923.
 39. H. Wang, R. Yan, Z. Li, X. Zhang and S. Zhang, *Catal. Commun.*, 2010, **11**, 763.
 40. A. Chinnappan and H. Kim, *RSC Adv.*, 2013, **3**, 3399.
 41. S. Sayyahi, A. Azin and S. J. Saghanezhad, *J. Mole. Liq.*, 2014, **198**, 30.
 42. A. Akbari, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2016, **57**, 431.
 43. S. Sayyahi, S. Shabani, S. Ghasemi, A. Azin and S. M. Hasani, *Oriental J. Chem.*, 2015, **31**, 1773.
 44. L. Yang, J. Xiong, H. Li, M. Zhang, W. Jiang, H. Liu, W. Zhu and H. Li, *RSC Adv.*, 2015, **5**, 104322.
 45. M. Muntzeck and R. Wilhelm, *Int. J. Mole. Sci.*, 2016, **17**, 860.
 46. H. Liu, R. Zhao, X. Song, F. Liu., S. Yu, S. Liu and X. Ge, *Catal. Lett.*, 2017, **147**, 2298.
 47. S. R. Thawarkar, N. D. Khupse and A. Kumar, *Chemistry Select*, 2017, **2**, 6833.
 48. M. Dashtban, A. Gilbert and P. Fatehi, *RSC Adv.*, 2014, **4**, 2037.
 49. P. C. Bruijninx and B. M. Weckhuysen, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2013, **52**, 11980.
 50. S. Jia, B. J. Cox, X. Guo, Z. C. Zhang and J. G. Ekerdt, "Catalysis of Lignin Depolymerization in Ionic Liquids". In Abstracts of Papers of the American Chemical Society, 240 : Amer. Chem. Soc., 1155 16th st, NW, Washington, DC 20036, USA, 2010.
 51. H. Zhao, J. E. Holladay, H. Brown and Z. C. Zhang, *Science*, 2007, **316**, 1597.
 52. X. Liang, G. Gong, H. Wu and J. Yang, *Fuel*, 2009, **88**, 613.
 53. N. A. S. Ramli and N. A. S. Amin, *BioEnergy Research*, 2017, **10**, 50.
 54. P. Brown, A. Bushmelev, C. P. Butts, J. Cheng, J. Eastoe, I. Grillo, R. K. Heenan and A. M. Schmidt, *Angew. Chem.*, 2012, **124**, 2464.
 55. P. Brown, A. Bushmelev, C. P. Butts, J.-C. Eloi, I. Grillo, P. J. Baker, A. M. Schmidt and J. Eastoe, *Langmuir*, 2013, **29**, 3246.
 56. S. Polarz, C. Bährle, S. Landsmann and A. Klaiiber, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2013, **52**, 13665.
 57. P. Brown, G. N. Smith, E. P. Hernández, C. James, J. Eastoe, W. C. Nunes, C. M. Settens, T. A. Hatton and P. J. Baker, *J. Phys. : Condensed Matter*, 2016, **28**, 176002.
 58. T. Khezeli and A. Daneshfar, *Ultrasonics Sonochemistry*, 2017, **38**, 590.
 59. A. García Saiz, P. Migowski, O. Vallcorba, J. Junquera, J. A. Blanco, J. A. González, M. T. Fernández Díaz, J. Rius, J. Dupont and J. Rodríguez Fernández, *Chemistry-A European Journal*, 2014, **20**, 72.
 60. K. D. Clark, M. M. Yamsek, O. Nacham and J. L. Anderson, *Chem. Commun.*, 2015, **51**, 16771.
 61. A. Klee, S. Prevost, W. Kunz, R. Schweins, K. Kiefer and M. Gradzielski, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.*, 2012, **14**, 15355.
 62. P. Brown, T. A. Hatton and J. Eastoe, *Current Opinion in Colloid & Interface Science*, 2015, **20**, 140.
 63. J. Jiang, Y. He, L. Wan, Z. Cui, Z. Cui and P. G. Jessop, *Chem. Commun.*, 2013, **49**, 1912.
 64. S. Sharma, N. Pal, P. K. Chowdhury, S. Sen and A. K. Ganguli, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2012, **134**, 19677.
 65. J. Xiong, W. Zhu, W. Ding, P. Wang, Y. Chao, M. Zhang, F. Zhu and H. Li, *RSC Adv.*, 2014, **4**, 40588.
 66. J. Dobson, *Gene Therapy*, 2006, **13**, 283.
 67. I. S. Lee, N. Lee, J. Park, B. H. Kim, Y.-W. Yi, T. Kim, T. K. Kim, I. H. Lee, S. R. Paik and T. Hyeon, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2006, **128**, 10658.
 68. P. Brown, A. M. Khan, J. P. Armstrong, A. W. Perriman, C. P. Butts and J. Eastoe, *Advanced Materials*, 2012, **24**, 6244.
 69. L. Xu, L. Feng, S. Dong and J. Hao, *Chem. Commun.*, 2015, **51**, 9257.
 70. C. J. Frégeau and A. De Moors, *Forensic Science International : Genetics*, 2012, **6**, 511.
 71. K. D. Clark, O. Nacham, H. Yu, T. Li, M. M. Yamsek, D. R. Ronning and J. L. Anderson, *Anal. Chem.*, 2015, **87**, 1552.
 72. L. Xu, Y. Wang, G. Wei, L. Feng, S. Dong and J. Hao, *Biomacromolecules*, 2015, **16**, 4004.